

README file

Data Set Title: CONSOLE_WP3_Task3.2_ Pan-EU survey of farmers and other rural landowners_FI_2022.11.03_v01.xlsx

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Data set contents

The data set consists of: Excel .xlsx file "CONSOLE_WP3_Task3.2_ Pan-EU survey of farmers and other rural landowners_FI_2022.11.03_v01.xlsx".

Data set documentation

Abstract

Data collected from the 409 Finnish farmers and 386 forests owners on their views on a result-based carbon compensation scheme.

Content of the files

The data set contains the choice experiment data sets for forest owners (data sheet: CE data forest owners) and farmers (data sheet: CE data farmers) and the other survey data that can be linked to the CE data sets with the respondent ID numbers. Variable coding follows the coding reported in the MS Excel file "CodesQuestionsAndVariableCoding_2022.11.03.xlsx".

File specifics

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Notes

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